

The Impact of Covid-19 on Life of Workers: A Special Case of Nagaland Economy

Dr M. Vadivel

Department of Economics
St. Joseph University, Dimapur, Nagaland, India
Corresponding Author: Dr M. Vadivel
Email: vadiveltt@gmail.com

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Abstract

No one escaped from atrocities of COVID-19 in the world wearing mask and taking vaccines in pandemic times. On Nagaland economy moreover, it squashed entire part of the economy. Nagaland has name for her green is located nearby Myanmar. Broadly to say, the impacts of covid-19 identified as worst play on Nagaland that encouraged more economic problems particularly non-availability of employment for agricultural and Industrial workers throughout. Due to arise of corona pandemic, life of all workers teared severely sans production in the total economy. More importantly examines economic losses of workers while facing unemployment, absence of materials, scarcity of food supply and sequence announcement of lockdown for pandemic period. In pandemic times, workers lost their jobs, cut the wage rates and following income also went down to hell. For instance, workers pushed to fall down face to extreme poverty condition. Workers abundantly expected more financial sources to compete with higher prices and repay higher interest rates to financial institutions.

Keywords

COVID-19, lock down, workers' income, job loss, nagaland, employment

Introduction

World Health Organization announced the name of the disease caused by the new outbreak of corona virus as COVID -19 on 11 February 2020. In Thailand which is also the first case of COVID-19 found outside China. While the threat of the pandemic COVID-19 is global and it knows no boundaries of class, caste, gender, religions, regions and languages, the poor and migrants are made most vulnerable, facing the threat of the virulent virus as well as the perils of unemployment and consequent hunger, even survival. All over the world, the surprise nationwide lockdown announced by the governments at the end of March. COVID-19

has disrupted life as normal in every aspects health, social, economic, environment, working culture, religious etc.

Covid-19 Cases in the World and India: According to situation report, India- WHO, the first confirmed case in India was detected in Kerala on 30 Jan. 2020 in a student returned from Wuhan City. On 14 March 2020 the confirmed cases reached to 84 and on 28 March it reached 909 in India. The government of India, under Prime Minister Narendra Modi declared a nationwide Lockdown on 24 March 2020 till 17 May 2020 (Nistula Hebbar, 2020). As on 26 May 2020 since after first case on 30 Jan 2020, India having 138,845 confirmed cases and 4,021 deaths with highest numbers includes the States of Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu and Gujarat. Since April, India has been battling an upsurge of the second wave of COVID-19 and across the country; hospitals are running out of beds, oxygen supply and medical supplies. Experts predict the surge will affect most states of India's northeast region. Close proximity and interconnectedness of the states make Nagaland very susceptible to a dangerous second wave.

Covid- Pandemic in Nagaland: As the virus spreads into the hilly remote areas of Nagaland, the villages in Nagaland are fighting the pandemic with the current healthcare infrastructure, challenging terrains for transfer of medical supplies, frequent power cuts, limited healthcare workers and inadequate medical supplies. Amid the alarming positivity trends, and increasing number of cases and deaths, the government has proactively begun to install oxygen plants and procure medical supplies. The COVID-19 pandemic reached the state of Nagaland on 22 May 2020, with its first case confirmed on 25 May 2020. Officially, Nagaland is the last of the northeastern states after Sikkim to report COVID-19 positive cases (Karmakar & Rahul, 2020). The returnees, mostly students and migrant workers, had started their journey from Chennai on 19 May.

Review of literature

Shivaji Sarkar (2021) mentioned that the repeated natural disasters and covid 19 lockdowns are taking a heavy toll on India's economy and hit the informal sectors most. The raging second covid wave is impacting states' finances. The centre government has released Rs 8837.6 crore in advance as the first installment of its share to State Disaster Response Fund (SDRF) for 2020-21. It is a huge sum for a country subsisting budget expenses on debt. Nicola et al. (2020) have summarized the socioeconomic outcomes of the COVID-19 pandemic. The demand for goods and service in all the sectors has decline drastically. Fear of buying due to measures like social distancing, isolating oneself, and complete ban on travels has led to shortages in stores. Healthcare and pharmaceutical industries have been experiencing a high healthcare cost and a huge shortage of medical institutions beds and PPE. Hospitality, tourism, and aviation industries are facing serious losses all over the world. The global oil price has dropped and reduction in chemical industry production has been predicted around 1.2 %. It has affected learners as instructional institutions stay closed.

Stojkoski et al. (2020) have analyzed the impact of socioeconomic factors like health infrastructure, demographic and economic determinants. The outcome exhibits that per capita income, population, and health spending have positive impact on COVID cases per million. Parameters like life expectancy, lack of hygiene, population density have a negative impact on the registered COVID-19 cases. Karmakar Sumir

(2020) reported that behalf of the North East Tea Association (NETA) states that Assam would be witnessing a loss of Rs. 1,218 crores in tea Industry due to Lockdown. Assam supplies more than 50% of India's tea production and due to prolonged lockdown 35% of the plantation needs to be skiffed, which will add to extra cost. Patel et al. (2020) the study spotlight the stumpy socioeconomic position causes by COVID-19 pandemic. Higher level of population, unemployment and fall in income conditions of workers working in unorganized sector suffer the most in almost all over the countries. According to him, poverty makes an individual more exposed and hence vulnerable to COVID-19. He then noted that the policymakers to introduce long-term legislation to improve social welfare measures.

Alstadsaeter et al. (2020) Finding shows that COVID-19 pandemic shock in Norway has a sturdy socio-economic inclined, as it has disproportionately affected the financially inclined population, including old age, parents with younger children. Beland et al. (2020) discuss mixed effects across occupations distribution and employees in the US economy. They show that occupations that have a higher share of employment working remotely were less affected by COVID-19. On the other hand, occupations with comparatively more workers working in proximity to others were more affected. They also find that occupations categorized as 'more exposed to disease' are less affected.

Bonadio et al. (2020) used quantitative methods to show a global lockdown as slimming down in labour supply for 64 countries. The authors find that the average decline in actual GDP constitutes a major contraction in economic activity, with a share attributed to disruptions in global supply chains. Elenev et al. (2020) explained the impact of COVID-19 as a fall in worker productivity and a decline in labor supply which subsequently affects firm revenue. The fall in income and the subsequent non-repayment of debt service obligations create a wave of corporate defaults, which might bring down financial intermediaries.

Methodology

For identify the impacts of Covid-19 on workers in specified region is not possible without appropriate data, at this point advantage of availed data report was carried out. Additionally, to distinguish explore the impacts on workers enlarge the scope to next level.

Study Area

The population of Nagaland as per Census 2011 is 19,78502 consisting of 953853 females which accounts for 48.21% of the total population and 1024649 which is 51.69% of the total population. The sex ratio is 931 females per 1000 males. During 2018, the female Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) was 13 compared to the male IMR of 2 and the overall IMR was 7, reduced substantially from 15.8 in 2011. However, Nagaland has lower IMR as compared with the national IMR. Registration of Live Births recorded for female and male were 21282 and 24387 respectively, while during 2018 it was recorded at 23757 and 23600 for male and females respectively. Below is the Nagaland district wise population as per Census 2011 and 2020 projection. Subsequent rises in Covid-19 cases, the government of Nagaland Tuesday announced a full lockdown for a week starting from 6 pm on May 14 and continue till May 21. The government had earlier announced stricter restrictions (but not a complete lockdown) from April 30 including closure of all education institutions, cinema halls and auditoriums, among others, as well as a curb on public gatherings.

These will continue till the new lockdown starts, the statement said. The decision comes in view of the recent surge in cases, especially in Kohima and Dimapur, with the latter reporting the highest number of active cases 1,633 as of May 7. Currently, the state has 2,884 active cases on Monday, 133 positive cases were reported. At least 10 people died, taking the toll to 150. The number of confirmed cases in entire North East reached to 50 on 17 March and 100 on 5 May 2020. For North eastern states, in Assam first case was confirmed on 31 March 2020. Nagaland has 03 fresh confirmed cases Nagaland has 03 confirmed cases, no death (Rahul Karmakar, 2020). On 25 May, the reported the first official cases in the state three people who returned from Chennai on 22 May tested positive for the novel coronavirus (Utpal Parashar , 2020). As of 26 June, the total number of cases in Nagaland was 371, including 209 active cases and 162 recoveries. On 20 July, total number of cases in Nagaland crossed 1000 mark (Outlook India, 2020).

Impacts of Covid19 on Life of Workers in the World: Global growth is estimated to have contracted by almost 5 percent in 2020, representing the largest economic crisis in a generation (World Bank, 2020). At the beginning of the year, at the onset of the pandemic, consumer spending began to decline dramatically, most notably in retail and recreation. By April, visits to restaurants, cafes, shopping centres, theme parks, museums, libraries, and movie theatres had declined globally by almost 60 percent. By December, almost 15 million airline flights had been cancelled, an average of 50,000 per day. While the global economy began to rebound in the summer, many countries were gripped by a second wave in the autumn and winter. Such dramatic economic downturns have had profound effects on the global labour market. As of January 2021, more than 90 percent of the world's workforce lived in countries where business closures were still in place for at least some economy sectors.

The COVID-19 pandemic has led to a dramatic loss of human life worldwide and presents an unprecedented challenge to public health, food systems and the world of work. The economic and social disruption caused by the pandemic is devastating: tens of millions of people are at risk of falling into extreme poverty, while the number of undernourished people, currently estimated at nearly 690 million, could increase by up to 132 million by the end of the year (Kimberly Chriscaden , 2020). Millions of enterprises face an existential threat, nearly half of the world's 3.3 billion global workforce are at risk of losing their livelihoods. Due to COVID-19 crisis many workers who have suffered job losses and Unemployment has also increased in many countries. Informal economy workers are particularly vulnerable, without source of an income earning during lockdowns they lose jobs, many are unable to feed themselves and their families. For most, no income means no food, or, at best, less food and less nutritious food being hardest hit. Further, when experiencing income losses, they may resort to negative coping strategies, such as distress sale of assets, predatory loans or child labour.

According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), global working hours declined by 17.3 percent in the second quarter of 2020. This is equivalent to 495 million full-time jobs lost. These dramatic reductions in working hours have been accompanied by equally dramatic reductions in income. Global labour income declined by 8.3 percent in 2020, amounting to a loss of USD 3.7 trillion, or 4.4 percent of global GDP. Roughly 178 million young people 1 in 4 of the global working population between the ages of 15 and 24 worked in the hardest-hit sectors when the pandemic began. Approximately, 1.6 billion informal sector workers have seen their hours decrease since the onset of the pandemic, in low-income countries drop earnings is estimated to be 86 percent. More than 75 percent of young workers are also informally employed. In low-

income countries, this percentage climbs to above 90 percent. Between February and July 2020, employment among adults declined by 5.1 percent, while employment among young adults fell by 17.4 percent, more than three times as much.

Impacts of Covid-19 on Life of Nagaland Workers: COVID-19 and its impacts on Nagas are observable at many levels. These disruptions invite reflections. Naga migrants apparently bear the most devastating impact of COVID-19 and the measure of lockdown. Migrants and their labours will continue to be needed for the economy. As reflect towards a life post-COVID-19 (Atola Longkumer, 2020).

Impact on Agriculture, Industry & Tourism: The lockdown came up in the harvesting season, due to which many of the crops got rotten in the field itself as the crops could not be supplied to the market due to lockdown. This has caused a heavy loss in the agriculture and rural economy as well. The lockdown has drastically brought down the production in various industries and tourism Industry in north eastern states including Nagaland (Bajaj Simran, 2020). The outbreak of COVID-19 and the disruption caused to the horticulture sector in Nagaland has negatively impacted the state's pineapple farmers. Organic pineapple is considered one of the signature crops of Nagaland. According to the Directorate of Horticulture in Nagaland, only 193 metric tons of pineapples were sold to Assam and 195 metric tons within the state till August 13. The price of a pineapple varies from Rs 15- 25 in wholesale. Pineapple seller also complained about reduced earnings due to lesser number of travelers on the highways. Farmers have planted more than 1 lakh pineapples in their farm. Due to pandemic even other production of agriculture commodities were also affected (Elithung Lotha, 2020).

Impacts on Economic Activities: Lockdowns and restrictions have led to a sharp impact on economic activities at the global and national level and the state has also not been spared. From 7.43 per cent growth during 2019-20, the state's economy is anticipated to register a negative growth of -5.59 per cent (Advanced Estimate) during 2020-21. In absolute terms, the contraction in the state economy is anticipated that the COVID-19 pandemic has been highly disruptive and challenging and it pulled down the state's economy to the tune of Rs 1013.11 crore during 2020-21 (Neiphiu Rio, 2021). He added in 2021, the State Plan size was Rs 639 crore on which a pro-rata cut of 15 per cent was applied, reducing the plan size to Rs 572 crore. However, keeping in view the need to give a boost to developmental activities, the state plan size for the current financial year has been enhanced to Rs 700 crore which represents an increase of over 22 per cent over the revised State Plan outlay of last year.

Table 1.1 Employment Generation in Nagaland under various schemes in last 3 years

Scheme	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
PMEGP- Estimated Employment Generated	7440	9664	9136*
MGNREGS-Person Day's Generated (in crore)	2.00	1.33	0.95**
DDU-GKY-No. of Candidates Placed in Jobs after Training	0	0	353
Day-NULM- No. of Skill Trained Persons given Placement	1749	0	0

Source: Ministry of Labour and Employment, Government of India.

Note: *(as on 31.12.2019) & **(as on 28.01.2020)

According to the Ministry of Labour and Employment, the estimated employment generated under PMREGP, the total beneficiaries /entrepreneurs in Nagaland for 2019-20 till December 31, 2019 was 9136. This was a fall from 9664 in 2018-19, after increasing from 7440, the previous year. As per the data provided by Rural Development (MIS), the 'Person days Generated' in Nagaland under MGNREGS, enacted as a security measure guaranteeing 100 days of wage employment per year to rural households, showed a declining trend. It declined from 2 crores 'Person days Generated' in 2017-18 to 1.33 crore in 2018-19. The figure for 2019-20 reflected a sharp decline to 0.95 crore till January 28, 2020. The State's ability to place candidates in jobs after training under DDU-GKY, a scheme implemented by the National Rural Livelihood Mission (NRLM) with the dual objectives of adding diversity to the incomes of rural poor families and cater to the career aspirations of rural youth, was less spectacular. Quoting the Ministry of Rural Development data, the Minister's reply informed that Nagaland managed to place 353 in the last three financial years, with the period from 2017-2019 showing '0' placement. Table depicted that life of workers particularly in Nagaland exaggerated by unemployment condition.

Impacts on Employment: Yhome highlighted the unresolved unemployment crisis in Nagaland. As per the data provided by the Employment Exchange, there is around 60,000 educated unemployed youth in the Exchange, there is around 60,000 educated unemployed youth in the state. In the nationwide race, Nagaland has the second highest Unemployment rate an average of 31% as against the national average of 6%, after Lakshadweep (Kesonyü Yhome, 2021).

Impacts of Market Situations: Nagaland no exception in suffering economical losses due to the Lockdown. All the hotels, restaurants, shopping malls, many marketplaces, etc are closed. Taxi services were also put on halt during the first two phases of Lockdown period. In India including the North East States 12.2 Crore people lost their jobs in the month of April and 27 million youths in the age group 20-30 years lost their jobs in April 2020 due to Lockdown (The hindu. (2020).

Impact on Mental status: The outbreak of COVID-19 outbreak has also created lots of tensions and anxiety in many people of Nagaland. People are getting distressed for being quarantined and many of them are trying to escape the quarantine center. The fear of the spread of the virus among people is on high rise. To help people manage their mental stress during this crisis.

Impacts on health sector: The second wave of covid-19 has hit Nagaland. Most hospitals and COVID-19 care centers are running with only a limited access to medical supplies and COVID-19 related equipment's as the wave surges on. Despite this, on May, Covid-19 hospitals are overwhelmed. There is an urgent need to supplement hospitals and health centers with the necessary medical equipment to treat Covid-19 patients. Procurement and distribution of medical supplies including but not limited to Oxygen concentrators, oxygen cylinders, pulse oximeters, PPE kits. These will be identified based on the needs as expressed by the Nagaland COVID War Room team and district hospitals. These will be distributed via three channels- through the Government, hospitals and NGOs.

Impact on Education: As all the educational Institutes are also closed, going as per the academic calendar is a major challenge. To tackle the situation Nagaland government has taken many initiatives apart from following the guidelines of UCG and Govt. of India. Some of them are- CR School in state which provide

the platform for all the schools to be available online for e- learning classes even Nagaland also followed (Arup Barman & Karan Das (2020)). All schools were locked to curb the speediness of virus.

Impact on Consumption pattern of petroleum Industry: In the month of April 2020 during 40 days of lockdown, the consumption of fuel products declined to 80% in India. This has caused the government of India to loss revenue of Rs. 40,000 Crore in the month of April (Beniwal V, and Chakraborty D. (2020)). Nagaland has become the first state in India to levy a COVID-19 cess on Rs 6 per litre of petrol and an extra Rs 5 per litre of diesel. Governor of Nagaland is notified that in addition to existing rate of tax and cess, the COVID-19 cess shall be levied (Sentiyanger Imchen (2021)). Similarly, the Assam govt. increased petrol price from Rs. 71.61 to Rs. 77.46 and of diesel from Rs. 67.07 to Rs. 70.50 per liter with effect from 22 April 2020 (Himanta Biswa Sarma, 2020).

Impacts on political policy and sectoral allocations: the budget for the year 2021-22 is affected by the financial crisis caused by the pandemic. However, seeing the steady pace of recovery of the country's economy and high expectations of a resurgent growth in the year ahead, the State Developmental Outlay for 2021-22 at ₹700 crores. This is an increase of 9.55% over the Plan size of 2020-21. State heavily dependent on Centrally Sponsored Schemes for most of the developmental activities, allocated ₹250 crores towards State Matching Share for Central Schemes including that of DoNER and NEC.

Table 1.2 Monthly COVID-19 Cases in Nagaland

Total cases	Recoveries	Deaths	Active case	Total
September 2020	4897	12	1058	5957
October 2020	5263	12	1221	6496
November 2020	9241	61	1442	10744
December 2020	10759	65	481	11305
January 2021	11733	88	107	11928
February 2021	11908	90	41	12039
March 2021	11952	91	15	12058
May 2021	9063	327	4923	14313

Source: Nagaland state Department of Health and Family Welfare

From the above table easily identified in the beginning the speediness of virus increased day by day death cases, active cases and active cases respectively. Then may 2021, it was declined due to usage of vaccination. To curb the pandemic vaccination is main tool as well as social distance and wear the masks because of it was included in analysis.

Data Analysis and Tools

Table 1.3 District Wise Cases registered of COVID-19 and Vaccination in Nagaland

District	Population+ (2020 est.)	Total cases	Recover ies	Deaths	Active case	No. Vaccinated**
Dimapur	431,845	13,286	11,900	360	1,026	1,38,958
Kiphire	84,365	228	200	8	20	9,123
Kohima	305,506	8,717	8,100	99	518	77,149
Longleng	57,552	253	206	2	45	24,386
Mokokchung	221,869	1,920	1,603	48	269	50,545
Mon	285,296	1,094	1,038	13	43	44,689
Peren	108,550	872	773	3	96	14,833
Phek	186,297	475	435	17	23	27,473
Tuensang	224,119	977	898	10	69	18,054
Wokha	189,631	316	265	11	40	27,049
Zunheboto	160,463	571	488	14	69	30,253
Total	2,255,493	28,709	25,906	585	2,218	4,62,512

Source: Government of Nagaland, As of 2021-08-09 "COVID cases source".

Source: + Population estimates for year of 2020.

**National Information Center, Government of Nagaland, 06/27/21.

Only secondary data collected and used correlation analysis for eleven districts of Nagaland which analyses the various impacts of COVID-19 on life of workers that have now not been covered due to the non-availability of data and briefly explained the atrocities of pandemic literarily. From observations of the above table in Nagaland state, Dimapur district had high level of cases compare with other district, data mentioned that there was mostly people affected by Covid-19 and 360 were died and followed by the capital of state Kohima district placed in second, here 99 were died due to corona diseases. Most of people of Longleng were died and Kiphire districts not affected heavily by corona only few killed 2 and 8 respectively.

Hypothesis Testing: Correlation analysis were carried out to identify the relationship between population and total covid-19 affected cases and taken vaccination by people in selected areas. The problem of the study investigates relationship between population and covid-19 cases and vaccination.

H1: There is significance relationship between population and covid-19 cases and vaccination.
Correlations

Table: 1.4: Pearson correlation: Pearson product correlation of population

	Population district wise	Total Cases	Vaccinated Cases
Population district wise	1		
Total Cases	.826**	1	
Vaccinated Cases	.881**	.954**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Reporting Pearson correlation: Pearson product correlation of population of eleven districts of Nagaland state was found high positive and statistically significant with total covid-19 cases ($r=.826, p < .001$) and vaccinated cases ($r=.881, p < .001$). Total cases very high positive and statistically significant with vaccinated cases ($r=.954, p < .001$). Hence H1 was supported this showed that increase in population density would lead to more covid-19 cases and vaccination in the followers. From this observation, when population density increases which would be lead to increase rate of covid-19 cases and people got aware to take more vaccination.

The above graphs explored the fact which mentioned the relationship between population and covid-19 cases and vaccination. Probed that population explosion is one of the resultant for unstable life of workers moreover other side corona contributed more to demolish them frequently. So, hereby evidenced that mostly numerous impacts lied on life of Nagaland workers in their soil.

Conclusion

Nagaland Chief Minister Neiphiu Rio said COVID-19 pandemic, to a future with high rates of sustained economic growth and better income levels for our citizens, the need for keeping a focus on saving livelihoods as well as lives during difficult times. Meanwhile actually in Nagaland workers were severely pretentious by countless causes on their life. They were spent lot of money instead of earning income when meets the loss of jobs, and debt burden, health expenses, transport charges were enlarged during the pandemic. By correlation analysis, we concluded this mostly in selected areas, covid-19 affected increased and got vaccination immediately because severe force of pandemic and impacts on ordinary business of life. No evidence to prove the impacts of covid-19 on life of workers, workers fell with lot of fights and conflicts to overcome it evidently.

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